

Morphometric Study of Clavicle in Eastern Indian Population with Reference to Volume & CurvatureSen S¹, Maity K², Biswas S.³¹Associate Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, KPC Medical College, Kolkata.²Assistant Professor, Dept. of ENT, JIS School of Medical Science & Research, Santragachi³Professor & HOD, Dept. of Anatomy, Calcutta National Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata

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Abstract:

Clavicle is a modified long bone. Its morphology is important in determining upper limb locomotion behavior. The morphometric parameters of this bone vary between left and right side and also between races and sex. It is a commonly fractured bone. Improved benefits derived from use of fixatives have resulted in renewed interest in interventional procedures in clavicle fracture. The knowledge of variation in curvatures and other parameters is indispensable for designing the intramedullary and external fixatives.

Keywords: Clavicle, Volume of Clavicle, Curvatures of Clavicle.

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Introduction

The human clavicle is described as a modified long bone. It is also known as collar bone and forms part of pectoral girdle. It has a shaft and two ends, sternal end and acromial end. The shaft is gently curved resembling letter 'f' with convexity forwards in medial two thirds and concavity forwards in lateral one thirds [1]. The clavicle has been considerably less studied from a comparative perspective than humerus and scapula. Clavicular morphology is important element in determining upper limb locomotion behaviour. The design of fixation device depends to a large extent on the anatomical and physical characters of this bone [2]. The bone is longer in broad shouldered male, and its curvatures are more pronounced than in female [3]

Clavicle fracture is a very common type of injury, and the break is always between costoclavicular and coracoclavicular ligaments, each of which is stronger than the clavicle itself [3]. The fracture occurs most frequently (80 -85%) in the middle third. The convention was to treat clavicular fracture in a conservative way. But, there is increasing recognition of the morbidity associated with displaced fracture and also increased rate of non-union of fractures in this zone. The improved benefits derived from fixation have resulted in renewed interest in fixation of clavicle fractures [4]. Intramedullary fixation is used increasingly to treat clavicular fractures. Along with the accepted mode of treatment of plate fixation, intramedullary fixation with a titanium elastic nail (TEN) is

gaining popularity [5]. So, it is becoming essential for the surgeon to know the normal anatomical variations of the clavicle, so as to apply the internal fixative methods successfully to secure clavicular fractures. Also, the knowledge of variations of curvatures of the bone is indispensable for designing the intramedullary or external fixatives to avoid post-operative complications like loosening of fixatives resulting in mal-union or non-union. A set of osteosynthesis plates that are adapted to the shape variation of human clavicles will not only reduce these complications but will also minimize the amount of bending required to adapt a plate to a specific clavicle during surgery. [6] Various studies have shown that the curvatures of clavicle varies between left and right sides. This is usually significant in case of adults [7]. This difference is absent in foetuses, newborns and children. With the use of right hand, the curve of the right clavicle in adults become greater than that of left side which lead to a shorter right bone as compared to the left one. It was found in other studies that, the medial angle of left clavicle was greater than that of the right one. The sum of the medial and lateral angles of left clavicle was greater than that of the right one. Also, the medial angles were greater than the lateral angles on both sided bones. [8,9,10].

Professor F.G. Parsons [11] (1916) did his renowned work on the proportions and characteristics of modern English clavicle. He examined 103 male clavicles and 80 female clavicles. There were definite evidences in his

study that the male bones were more curved than the females and in both the sexes the right bone is more curved than the left one. He presumed that these variations in parameters may be due to two possible reasons -firstly, more constant use of right hand led to increased curvature of the right sided clavicle, thus bringing the two ends nearer; and secondly, it might lead to an earlier bony union of the epiphyses, which would stop further growth. Studies has been done all over the world among different groups of population to ascertain variations in external and internal contours of clavicle. All the studies have pointed out that obvious differences exist in various parameters of the bone. The variations in dimensions and contour of clavicle among different groups of population from different races point towards the implication of this bone in determination of identity (eg. - race, sex, stature, etc.) of a person from skeletal remains.

Keeping these clinical and anthropological implications in view, the present study is an attempt to know the angulation and volume of clavicle with regard to right and left variations.

Aims & Objectives

The aim of this study is to make a comparison between contours of left and right clavicles with special regard to volume and angulation among a defined population. With regard to the change in protocol of surgical treatment of clavicular fracture,

a clear idea about the variations in dimensions and parameters of clavicles between left and right side will be helpful in orthopaedics field. The studies performed among various populations of varied countries and origin, have shown that there are variations in dimensions and contours of left and right clavicles. So, addition of few more pages to the literature of our predecessors will help in anthropological studies.

Specific Objectives

1. To determine the volume and curvature of the clavicle.
2. To ascertain any variations in parameters between left and right sided clavicles.

Materials & Methods

The study was done by measuring 156 clavicles of both right and left sides. Among them, 73 was right sided and 83 were left sided. The samples were collected from departmental collections of Department of Anatomy, Nilratan Sircar Medical College and Hospital, SSKM & IPGMER, Calcutta Medial College & Hospital, R.G.KAR Medical College & Hospital. Students of First Professional MBBS course of N.R.S.M.C&H also provided bones from their own collection. The morphometric study was done in NRS Medical College and data were collected on various parameters. The samples were collected by simple random method and the study design is observational quantitative type.

Figure 1: A part of total number of clavicles examined (both right & left sided)

Inclusion Criteria:

Dry adult clavicles were taken for measurements. The bones had completed ossification and without any deformity or signs of injury, or tumour or other pathological conditions. 73 number of clavicles were right sided and 83 number were left sided. The bones were cleaned and cleared of dust etc and divided into two groups according to the side of the

body it belonged to. The different parameters were measured as follows:

1. **Volume Of Clavicle-** To measure the volume of clavicle, each bone was taken and one end was tied with a string. A 500c.c measuring cylinder was filled with water upto the 400c.c. marking.

Then each bone was dipped into the water longitudinally by holding the tied string, until it was completely immersed.

The difference in level of water was measured which denoted the volume of the bone. Each vol-

ume was measured twice and average of the two values was taken. Before the measurement of volume of each new bone, water was replaced in the cylinder to ensure correct level i.e. at 400c.c.

Figure 2 & 3: Figures showing method of measuring volume of clavicle

2. Curvature of Clavicle: The curvature of clavicle is denoted by the summation of the inner and outer angles. To measure the curves of the clavicle, the method described by Parsons (1916) [11] was followed.

The clavicle was placed on a white paper with its anterior and posterior borders in the same horizontal plane. The midpoints of the sternal and acromial ends were marked and denoted as 'a' & 'b' respectively and were joined by a straight line. The central axis of the bone was drawn as a curved line, midway between anterior and posterior borders throughout the whole length. This curved line has two convexities, the medial two-thirds was convex

anteriorly while lateral one-third was convex posteriorly. The deepest point on the two curves of the clavicle where the convexities were the maximum, were marked as points 'c' and 'd'.

These points were again joined by a straight line. Finally, point 'a' was joined with point 'c' and point 'b' was joined with point 'd'. Thus, two angles were formed: a medial angle 'acd' which gave the curvature of medial two-thirds, and a lateral angle 'cdb' which indicated the curvature of lateral one-third. These angles were measured with the help of a protractor. The sum of the two angles constituted the total curvature of the clavicle i.e. index of curvature as depicted by Parsons. [11]

Figure 4: Contour of right clavicle as seen from above

- a: midpoint of sternal end.
- b: midpoint of acromial end.

- c: deepest point of medial curvature.
- d: deepest point of lateral curvature.
- acd: medial angle.
- cdb: lateral angle.

Results: The study done with 156 dry clavicles of both sides and the measurements were recorded. Data collected from individual bone was tabulated. The results came out as follows:-

Table 1: Volume

	Right Clavicles	Left Clavicles
Range	10-30 c.c	10-35 c.c
Mean	20.49 c.c	20.37 c.c
Standard Dev	6.55	6.15

p-0.906

Figure 5:

The volumes were measured by water displacement method showed almost equal values on right (20.49 c.c) and left sided clavicles (20.37c.c). With a 'p' value of 0.9, the difference was statistically insignificant.

Table 1: Medial Angle

	Right Clavicles	Left Clavicles
Range	142 ⁰ -170 ⁰	142 ⁰ -167 ⁰
Mean	153.57 ⁰	154.01 ⁰
Standard Dev	6.24	5.68

p-0.65

Figure 6:
Table 2: Lateral Angle

	Right Clavicles	Left Clavicles
Range	140 ⁰ -168 ⁰	132 ⁰ -170 ⁰
Mean	153.89 ⁰	157.02 ⁰
Standard Dev	6.29	7.64

p-0.0058

Figure 7:

Table 3: Total Angle

	Right Clavicles	Left Clavicles
Range	283.5 ⁰ -332 ⁰	283.5 ⁰ -335 ⁰
Mean	307.43 ⁰	311.03 ⁰
Standard Dev	10.48	11.18

p-0.04

Figure 8:

The mean value of medial angles of right sided clavicles is 153.57° and that of the left side is 154.01° . They differed by 0.44° , the medial angle of the left clavicles being slightly greater. But this difference is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.65$). The mean lateral angle of right clavicles is 153.89° and that on the left side is 157.02° . The difference is 3.13° , the angle on the left side being greater. This difference is statistically significant with a 'p' value of 0.005. Now, on the left sided clavicles, the mean values of medial and lateral angles were compared and 'p' value of 0.004 was obtained. That means, in case of left clavicles, the medial and lateral curvatures had a statistically significant difference. In case of the right sided clavicles, the difference between means of medial and lateral angles was insignificant with a 'p' value of 0.76. The total angle, i.e summation of medial and lateral angles of each clavicle denotes the index of curvature of that bone. The difference between the means of the right and left sided clavicles is statistically significant ($p = 0.04$).

Discussions:

Volume: The volume of each bone was measured by water displacement method. The range of volume of the right sided clavicles was found to be 10 c.c. to 30 c.c. and that of the left side was 10c.c to 35c.c. On the right side, the mean volume was 20.49 c.c with a standard deviation of 6.55. The values for the left side was 20.37c.c and 6.15c.c as mean and standard deviation respectively. With a 'p' value of 0.9, the difference is insignificant. References are very few regarding the circumference, weight and volume of clavicles. The dissertation submitted by Dr Sobha [12], contains comparisons between right and left sided clavicles on these parameters of clavicle. In that study, the volume of clavicles came out as 17.52 c.c and 12.57 c.c in case of right sided male and female

clavicles respectively. On the left side, the volumes were 17.86 c.c and 11.3 c.c for males and females respectively. All the differences in different parameters of this study were found to be statistically significant. In the present study of eastern Indian clavicles, the differences between the means volumes of right and left sided clavicles were found to be statistically insignificant.

Curvature of Clavicle:-

Many workers have attempted to determine angular difference between left and right sided clavicles. The average angle of curvatures of clavicle was found to vary among different races, as reported by many authors. Parson FG [11] observed that medial angle of English clavicle was 1540 on right and 1540 on the left. These values are very near to those found in present study. He also found the lateral angle to be 1490 on the right and 149.50 on the left. These values are less than those found in the present study. There was no difference between right and left in his study. The summation of medial and lateral angles (index of curvature) of English clavicle was 302.50 on right and 303.50 on the left. Both these values are less than those found in present study. This suggested that the clavicles of Eastern Indian population are less curved than that of English population. Terry RJ [13] found the mean medial and lateral angles of American Negroes were 152.320 and 141.240 on the right and 152.600 and 144.680 on the left side respectively. The sum of both angles were 292.940 on the right and 296.420 on the left. The values of medial angle was very near to that of the present study, but the lateral angles were much less. Hence, the clavicles of Eastern Indian people are less curved than the Americans on the lateral side. In a study done by Oliver G [14] among French people, the average medial angle was 150.600 on the right side and 151.400 on the left side. The average lateral angles

were 143.400 on the right and 143.00 on the left. All these values were less than the present study. The sum of both angles of French clavicle were 294.250 on right and 294.400 on the left side. There was almost no difference between curvatures of right and left sided clavicles.

Therefore, the French clavicles are more curved than eastern Indian clavicles. Kaur H [8] et al observed in the north western Indian population, that the average medial angle of clavicle was 151.680 on the right and 151.890 on the left. Those of the lateral angles were 143.960 on right side and 148.460 on the left side. The total angles were 292.550 on right and 297.180 on the left. All these values are less than those of present study, suggesting the eastern clavicles to be less curved than the North West Indian clavicles.

The study done by Nagarchi et al [2] on MBBS students of different medical colleges of south India, pointed out the range of medial angle of right clavicle to be 1360-1630 and that of the left was 1350-1660. The range of lateral angle was 1220-1620 on right and 1260-1680 on the left. They did not compare the mean and no conclusion was drawn on statistical significances of the differences. But their study definitely added to the morphometric values of clavicle. Dzhigora S [15] observed medial curvature to be greater than lateral curvature. But in the present study, the medial and lateral angles of the right side varied insignificantly. But, the difference between the means of medial and lateral angles on the left side was 3 degrees. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.004$). Therefore, the designing of surgical fixative for the left sided clavicles must be done considering this discrepancy of inner and outer angles.

The mean value of medial angles of the right and left sided clavicles varied insignificantly. But, the difference in lateral angles on two sides showed statistically significant difference ($p < 0.005$). That means, in fracture lateral third of clavicle, the fixation device must be designed keeping this bilateral discrepancy of lateral angles in mind. In displaced lateral third clavicular fracture, fixed by Krischner wire with tension band wiring with four-hole hook plate and early mobilisation gave excellent result. [16] The attachment of a fixation device can be easily achieved at medial end. Laterally, the narrowness of supero-inferior dimensions restricts application of fixation devices. The difference between total angles of left and right sides was also found to be significant. Thus, the index of curvature [11], i.e summation of medial and lateral angles was found to be more on left side (311.030) than that on the right side (307.430), making the left sided clavicles less curved than the right sided clavicles among Eastern Indian people.

Conclusion:

The study of morphometric analysis of clavicles in Eastern Indian population was done on individual bones and data recorded (73 right clavicles and 83 left clavicles, total 156). The various parameters measured were volume, medial angle, lateral angle and total angle i.e Index of curvature. Statistical analysis was done on the collected data and the values were compared to find out whether the differences were statistically significant or not. The findings were corroborated with the findings of similar studies done by various workers among populations of different zones of India and other countries. Some results were in accordance to the present study and some were not.

We conclude from our study of clavicles of eastern Indian population, that, there is wide variation between the different parameters studied and compared with results obtained from observations of other workers. The index of curvature was found to be more on left side (311.03⁰) than that on the right side (307.43⁰), making the left sided clavicles less curved than the right sided clavicles among Eastern Indian people, probably due to more use of right hand. Unlike the right clavicles, the inner and outer curvatures varied significantly in case of the left sided bones. Also, the lateral curvature showed significant discrepancy between two sides. In fracture lateral third of clavicle, the fixation device must be designed and intra medullary fixation must be done, keeping this bilateral discrepancy of lateral angles in mind. The right sided clavicles were found to be significantly heavier than the left sided bones. The volume and circumference was almost equal on two sides. Thus, in our own small way, we have tried to add few pages to the works of our predecessors on morphometry of clavicles and their bilateral variations.

These parameters are of great importance while considering surgical fixation. It will also be helpful in anthropology and forensic practices.

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